

Excess molar volume, excess energy and viscosity deviation of binary mixtures of tetrahydrofuran with some hydrocarbons at various temperatures

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The density and viscosity of the binary mixtures of tetrahydrofuran with normal pentane, hexane and heptane have been measured as a function of the composition at 288.15, 293.15 and 298.15 K. From these data, excess molar volume, excess free energy, deviation in viscosity of the composition and the interaction parameter of Grunberg and Nissan have been calculated. All the derived parameters are found to be either negative or positive over the entire range of composition depending on the molecular interactions and the nature of the binary liquid mixtures. The results have been interpreted in terms of possible molecular interactions existing between the components of these mixtures.

Grouping of solvents into classes often is based on the nature of the intermolecular forces because the manner whereby solute and solvent molecules are associated with one another brings about a marked effect on the resulting properties. After the introduction of the concept of ionization power of solvent¹, much work has been devoted to the solvent effects on the rate and equilibrium processes². Because of the close connection between liquid structure and macroscopic properties, determination of volumetric and viscometric properties is a valuable tool to learn the liquid state³. On the other hand, the obtaining of reliable measurements of solvent properties over a wide range of composition, pressure and temperature often is not feasible; hence, prediction and correlation methods constitute a valuable option to overcome such difficulties^{4,5}.

The present work deals with to the study of the structure and interactions in THF + hydrocarbon mixtures. Tetrahydrofuran (THF) is a good industrial solvent. It figures prominently in the high energy battery industry and has found its applications in organic syntheses as evident from its physicochemical studies^{6,7}. Since no reports are available of density and viscosity studies of tetrahydrofuran (THF) with normal aliphatic hydrocarbons, the effect of chain-length of hydrocarbons (C₅, C₆, C₇) on these properties of binary mixtures of tetrahydrofuran with normal hydrocarbons at 288.15, 293.15 and 298.15 K is reported in the present investigation.

Results and discussion

The physical properties of tetrahydrofuran (THF), normal pentane, hexane and heptane at various temperatures

are given in Table 1. The experimental values of mole-fractions (X_1), densities (ρ), viscosities and various derived parameters of the different binary mixtures of solvents studied here at different temperatures are recorded in Table 2.

The experimental density (ρ) values (Table 1) have been used to calculate the excess molar volume (V_m^E), viscosity deviation ($\Delta\eta$), excess Gibbs free energy (G^{*E}) and interaction parameter (d) using the following eqs.⁸ (1-4) :

$$V_m^E = \frac{M}{\rho} - \sum_{i=1}^c x_i \frac{M_i}{\rho_i} \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta\eta = \eta - \sum_{i=1}^c x_i \eta_i \quad (2)$$

$$G^{*E} = RT \ln \frac{\eta M}{\rho} - RT \sum_{i=1}^c x_i \ln \frac{\eta_i M_i}{\rho_i} \quad (3)$$

$$\ln \eta = \sum_{i=1}^c x_i \ln \eta_i + d \prod_{i=1}^c x_i \quad (4)$$

where c stands for the number of components of the mixture, M and M_i are the molar mass of the mixture and of the pure components, ρ and ρ_i represent the density of the mixture and pure components, η and η_i are the corresponding viscosities, R is the gas constant and T is the temperature in Kelvin. The values of these functions and d are presented in Table 2 along with the values of ρ , η and mole fraction.

Table 1. Physical properties of tetrahydrofuran, n-pentane, n-hexane and n-heptane at various temperatures

T/K	$\rho \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg m}^{-3}$		$\eta/\text{m.Pa.S}$	
	This Work	Literature	This Work	Literature
		Tetrahydrofuran (THF)		
288.15	0.88720	0.88720 ¹⁹	0.50924	0.50923 ¹⁹
293.15	0.88358	0.88357 ¹⁹	0.49107	0.49106 ¹⁹
298.15	0.87888	0.87888 ¹⁹	0.45999	0.45999 ¹⁹
		n-Pentane		
288.15	0.62528	0.62527 ¹⁶⁻¹⁸	0.23145	0.23144 ¹⁶⁻¹⁸
293.15	0.62131	0.62132 ¹⁶⁻¹⁸	0.21996	0.21995 ¹⁶⁻¹⁸
298.15	0.61883	0.61883 ¹⁶⁻¹⁸	0.21210	0.21210 ¹⁶⁻¹⁸
		n-Hexane		
288.15	0.66125	0.66124 ¹⁶⁻¹⁸	0.33381	0.33381 ¹⁶⁻¹⁸
293.15	0.65472	0.65471 ¹⁶⁻¹⁸	0.31256	0.31225 ¹⁶⁻¹⁸
298.15	0.65253	0.65252 ¹⁶⁻¹⁸	0.29191	0.29190 ¹⁶⁻¹⁸
		n-Heptane		
288.15	0.68192	0.68192 ¹⁶⁻¹⁸	0.42121	0.42121 ¹⁶⁻¹⁸
293.15	0.67951	0.67950 ¹⁶⁻¹⁸	0.40020	0.40010 ¹⁶⁻¹⁸
298.15	0.67669	0.67669 ¹⁶⁻¹⁸	0.38450	0.38450 ¹⁶⁻¹⁸

The excess molar volume were correlated by Redlich-Kister equation.

$$V_m^E = X_1 X_2 \sum a_i (x_1 - x_2)^i \quad (5)$$

The coefficient in eq. (5) was estimated by the least-squares fit method, where the squares of the difference between the calculated and experimental excess molar volumes results is minimized. The optimal values of the coefficients in eq. (5) are listed in Table 3. The standard deviation was calculated by

$$\sigma (V_m^E) = [(V_{m \text{ expt}}^E - V_{m \text{ cal}}^E)]^2 / (D - N)^{0.5} \quad (6)$$

where D and N are the number of data points and parameters, respectively. The experimental values of $\Delta\eta$ are also reported in Table 1. The viscosity deviations were correlated by the following equation :

$$Q = X_1 X_2 \sum H_i (x_1 - x_2)^i \quad (7)$$

where $Q = \Delta\eta/(\text{m.Pa.S})$. The coefficient in eq. (7) are also regressed by employing the least square fit method. Standard deviations for the viscosity calculations were determined by eq. (8).

$$\sigma (\Delta\eta) = [\sum (\Delta\eta_{\text{expt}} - \Delta\eta_{\text{cal}})]^2 / (D - N)^{0.5} \quad (8)$$

The optimal parameters in correlating deviations of viscosity are listed in Table 4.

From Table 2 it is observed that the values of V_m^E for all

binary mixtures THF + n-pentane, THF + n-hexane and THF + n-heptane at different temperatures over the entire composition are positive indicating the mutual dissociation of the component molecules. Because of the small difference in the molar volumes of the components, tetrahydrofuran will not fit into the structure of the normal aliphatic hydrocarbons (C_5H_{12} , C_6H_{14} , C_7H_{16}), thereby increasing the volume of the mixture⁹. Positive V_m^E also suggests that the dispersion forces prevail between THF and normal hydrocarbons.

It is also found from Table 2 that the difference in the molar volumes of the mixtures of the components follows the following order : THF + n-heptane > THF + n-hexane > THF + n-pentane at any temperature studied here. This indicates the higher value of V_m^E for THF + n-pentane mixture than that of THF + n-hexane mixture which is in turn higher than that of THF + n-heptane (shown in Table 2).

There is a systematic increase in V_m^E with a rise in temperature for all mixtures studied here and such changes or variations are evident from Table 2. This increase in V_m^E with temperature is as expected from theoretical considerations¹⁰.

Deviations in viscosity ($\Delta\eta$) shown in Table 2 for the mixtures of tetrahydrofuran (THF) with normal aliphatic hydrocarbons (C_5 - C_7) are negative which increase with increasing size of hydrocarbons. The trend in $\Delta\eta$ is THF- C_5H_{12} < THF- C_6H_{14} < THF- C_7H_{16} . The dominance of exo-

Table 2. Density (ρ), viscosity (η), excess molar volume (V_m^E), viscosity deviation ($\Delta\eta$), excess free energy of activation of viscous flow (G^{*E}), interaction parameter (d) and mole fractions of tetrahydrofuran (X_1) with different normal hydrocarbons at various temperatures

X_1	$\rho \times 10^{-3}$ kg m ⁻³	η /m.Pa.S	V_m^E /cm ³ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta\eta$ /m.Pa.S	G^{*E} J mol ⁻¹	d
288.15 K						
THF + n-Pentane						
0	0.62528	0.23145	0	0	0	0
0.10005	0.64384	0.24404	0.08012	-0.01520	-48.30241	-0.28795
0.20009	0.66314	0.25863	0.22501	-0.02841	-85.07026	-0.29207
0.30012	0.68356	0.27829	0.38213	-0.03653	-87.33218	-0.24928
0.40013	0.70536	0.29859	0.52531	-0.04401	-98.96688	-0.25388
0.50014	0.72910	0.32188	0.60112	-0.04850	-103.43975	-0.25829
0.60013	0.75389	0.34765	0.75452	-0.05051	-104.11553	-0.27671
0.70012	0.78256	0.38240	0.65501	-0.04354	-70.39536	-0.23806
0.80009	0.81536	0.41850	0.35254	-0.03521	-57.71623	-0.24135
0.90005	0.85002	0.46314	0.15231	-0.01833	-19.71319	-0.17868
1	0.88720	0.50924	0	0	0	0
THF + n-Hexane						
0	0.66125	0.33381	0	0	0	0
0.11713	0.67683	0.34235	0.31001	-0.01201	-27.52968	-0.23410
0.22998	0.69396	0.35205	0.47510	-0.02211	-52.41408	-0.24807
0.33863	0.71227	0.36440	0.58502	-0.03002	-63.79133	-0.24709
0.44335	0.73168	0.37894	0.67511	-0.03265	-65.71838	-0.24491
0.54436	0.75343	0.39784	0.59002	-0.03147	-50.21391	-0.21945
0.64184	0.77676	0.41661	0.47512	-0.02980	-43.40952	-0.21533
0.73598	0.80164	0.43672	0.36013	-0.02631	-36.22659	-0.21676
0.82695	0.82184	0.45847	0.25003	-0.02041	-27.60456	-0.22318
0.91491	0.85643	0.48214	0.14561	-0.01217	-17.23062	-0.24081
1	0.88720	0.50924	0	0	0	0
THF + n-Heptane						
0	0.68192	0.42121	0	0	0	0
0.13376	0.69798	0.42314	0.01801	-0.00984	-7.43921	-0.17964
0.25784	0.71408	0.42721	0.16810	-0.01670	-7.72454	-0.18181
0.37327	0.73105	0.43212	0.29111	-0.02175	-9.27331	-0.19153
0.48091	0.74900	0.43746	0.38112	-0.02608	-17.43592	-0.21398
0.58153	0.76886	0.44679	0.32102	-0.02561	-12.01893	-0.21126
0.67580	0.78996	0.45649	0.24515	-0.02421	-11.42528	-0.21828
0.76430	0.81226	0.46761	0.17321	-0.02088	-9.62714	-0.22511
0.84753	0.83579	0.47985	0.11213	-0.01597	-8.13692	-0.23610
0.92597	0.86066	0.49304	0.06122	-0.00968	-7.39667	-0.26666
1	0.88720	0.50924	0	0	0	0
293.15 K						
THF + n-Pentane						
0	0.62131	0.21996	0	0	0	0
0.10005	0.63975	0.23307	0.10009	-0.01401	-40.13625	-0.24946
0.20009	0.65882	0.24979	0.28215	-0.02442	-52.82306	-0.20946
0.30012	0.67932	0.26882	0.42501	-0.03250	-58.50596	-0.19254

Table-2 (contd.)

0.40013	0.70091	0.28943	0.60002	-0.03901	-64.64248	-0.19537
0.50014	0.72427	0.31156	0.72551	-0.04399	-74.89723	-0.21415
0.60013	0.74962	0.33706	0.80432	-0.04560	-76.91300	-0.22744
0.70012	0.77846	0.36856	0.68511	-0.04121	-61.08626	-0.21975
0.80009	0.81076	0.40335	0.44004	-0.03352	-50.21842	-0.22649
0.90005	0.84594	0.44846	0.18603	-0.01551	-5.25559	-0.11664
1	0.88358	0.49107	0	0	0	0
THF + n-Hexane						
0	0.65472	0.31256	0	0	0	0
0.11713	0.67030	0.32340	0.34011	-0.01001	-13.78878	-0.18204
0.22998	0.68750	0.33559	0.52012	-0.01802	-24.35637	-0.18527
0.33863	0.70596	0.34898	0.63510	-0.02403	-31.96879	-0.19098
0.44335	0.72573	0.36001	0.70001	-0.03169	-61.24642	-0.23893
0.54436	0.74763	0.37971	0.62503	-0.03002	-41.13155	-0.20693
0.64184	0.77130	0.40073	0.50002	-0.02640	-22.50561	-0.18047
0.73598	0.79649	0.42074	0.38215	-0.02320	-18.26332	-0.18161
0.82695	0.82346	0.44201	0.26002	-0.01817	-14.90494	-0.18918
0.91491	0.385273	0.46499	0.10003	-0.01089	-11.68659	-0.20717
1	0.88358	0.49107	0	0	0	0
THF + n-Heptane						
0	0.67951	0.40020	0	0	0	0
0.13376	0.69541	0.40303	0.03211	-0.00932	-6.19986	-0.17964
0.25784	0.71116	0.40749	0.23101	-0.01614	-6.62451	-0.18181
0.37327	0.72815	0.41302	0.32905	-0.02110	-8.97066	-0.19153
0.48091	0.74110	0.41907	0.39811	-0.02483	-14.95693	-0.21398
0.58153	0.76587	0.42849	0.33521	-0.02455	-10.38316	-0.21126
0.67580	0.78682	0.43850	0.26115	-0.02302	-9.17771	-0.21828
0.76430	0.80901	0.44949	0.18522	-0.02016	-8.91551	-0.22511
0.84753	0.83246	0.46185	0.11609	-0.01537	-7.42920	-0.23610
0.92597	0.85715	0.47507	0.06713	-0.00927	-7.24725	-0.26666
1	0.88358	0.49107	0	0	0	0
298.15 K						
THF + n-Pentane						
0	0.61884	0.21210	0	0	0	0
0.10005	0.63627	0.22409	0.25510	-0.01281	-37.51550	-0.24948
0.20009	0.65502	0.24048	0.46001	-0.02122	-39.51000	-0.18319
0.30012	0.67532	0.25800	0.59870	-0.02850	-45.81660	-0.17346
0.40013	0.69680	0.27677	0.75420	-0.03452	-54.29800	-0.18177
0.50014	0.71991	0.29768	0.88000	-0.03840	-59.58580	-0.19288
0.60013	0.74504	0.32036	0.94801	-0.04051	-67.55300	-0.21753
0.70012	0.77317	0.34700	0.87505	-0.03865	-66.34380	-0.23686
0.80009	0.80424	0.38003	0.71900	-0.03040	-43.53820	-0.22629
0.90005	0.84004	0.42120	0.34599	-0.01401	-1.44872	-0.11918
1	0.87888	0.45999	0	0	0	0

THF + n-Hexane						
0	0.65253	0.29191	0	0	0	0
0.11713	0.66764	0.30251	0.40111	-0.00909	-10.00730	-0.17017
0.22998	0.68449	0.31417	0.61002	-0.01546	-19.08990	-0.17560
0.33863	0.70279	0.32582	0.71502	-0.02155	-34.60930	-0.19689
0.44335	0.72236	0.33805	0.77501	-0.02838	-51.08960	-0.24782
0.54436	0.74425	0.35700	0.66541	-0.02748	-28.97290	-0.18652
0.64184	0.76770	0.37358	0.53021	-0.02621	-17.33250	-0.17095
0.73598	0.79261	0.39434	0.41001	-0.02127	-15.01330	-0.17459
0.82695	0.81936	0.41503	0.27512	-0.01587	-7.93677	-0.16881
0.91491	0.84793	0.43648	0.15003	-0.00921	-4.84634	-0.17684
1	0.87888	0.45999	0	0	0	0
THF + n-Heptane						
0	0.67669	0.38450	0	0	0	0
0.13376	0.69246	0.38606	0.05512	-0.00854	-5.49011	-0.17200
0.25784	0.70808	0.38915	0.26102	-0.01481	-5.70903	-0.17872
0.37327	0.72492	0.39354	0.35621	-0.01914	-6.60921	-0.18669
0.48091	0.74273	0.39842	0.41111	-0.02238	-11.48670	-0.20288
0.58153	0.76231	0.40609	0.35005	-0.02231	-8.35571	-0.20388
0.67580	0.78308	0.41463	0.28106	-0.02089	-6.83200	-0.20859
0.76430	0.80505	0.42423	0.19514	-0.01797	-5.56499	-0.21470
0.84753	0.82828	0.43559	0.13008	-0.01289	-4.67554	-0.21027
0.92597	0.85272	0.44651	0.07201	-0.00789	-3.80617	-0.24030
1	0.87888	0.45999	0	0	0	0

Table 3. Regression results for the excess volumes of THF + normal hydrocarbons mixture at various temperatures

System	Temp. K	a_0	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	a_5	δ
THF + n-Pentane	288.15	2.66282	2.02386	-2.08350	2.84555	-	-	0.04050
	293.15	2.97246	1.88985	-2.06088	-2.33610	-	-	0.018708
	298.15	3.54241	1.34718	-	-	-	-	0.034120
THF + n-Hexane	288.15	2.54097	-1.28838	-2.09799	2.60345	3.22786	-2.98877	0.013813
	293.15	2.60473	-1.06502	0.49835	-	-	-	0.017298
	298.15	2.80351	-1.36760	-	-	-	-	0.019951
THE + n-Heptane	288.15	1.44615	-0.014286	-2.62717	1.14038	1.61289	-	0.011453
	293.15	1.50759	-0.48406	-1.68899	1.68368	-	-	0.011274
	298.15	1.58020	-0.55754	-1.53455	1.66353	-	-	0.009582

thermic enthalpy of mixing over endothermic mixing resulting tetrahydrofuran (THF)-hydrocarbon interaction, leads to less negative $\Delta\eta$ values for higher aliphatic hydrocarbons than for lower ones²¹. It seems that in tetrahydrofuran + hydrocarbon systems, the forces between pairs of unlike molecules are far less than that between pairs of like molecules. Therefore, the binary mixtures of tetrahydrofuran with higher hydrocarbons are less fluid due to enhanced non-covalent forces between like molecules. Negative $\Delta\eta$

values in the present investigation can also be attributed to unequal molecular sizes of the constituent molecules of the mixture where dispersion forces are dominant¹².

The effect of temperature increase is to disrupt hetero and homo association of the molecules which causes increase in fluidity of the liquid. So, $\Delta\eta$ values are higher at higher temperatures. Similar results was obtained as reported earlier¹³.

Table 4. Regression results for the deviation of viscosity of THF + normal hydrocarbons mixture at various temperatures

System	Temp. K	a_0	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	δ
THF + n-Pentane	288.15	0.19448	-0.03755	-	-	-	0.001113
	293.15	0.17614	-0.04281	-	-	-	0.001459
	298.15	-0.15715	-0.04444	-	-	-	0.001574
THF + n-Hexane	288.15	-0.13108	-0.01022	-	-	-	0.000923
	293.15	-0.11682	-0.01651	-	-	-	0.001417
	298.15	-0.11033	-0.01977	0.02744	-	-	0.000948
THE + n-Heptane	288.15	-0.10213	-0.02881	-	-	-	0.000533
	293.15	-0.09863	-0.02359	0.02062	-0.00971	-0.04866	0.000267
	298.15	-0.08840	-0.02129	-	-	-	0.000322

The negative values of excess Gibbs free energy of flow (shown in Table 2) for tetrahydrofuran + n-hydrocarbons over the entire range of composition and temperature which indicate the formation of molecular complex between unlike molecules through non-covalent bonds. Subba *et al.*¹⁴ made a similar observation from G^*E studies for the binary mixtures of propionic acid and alcohols.

The positive values of Grunberg and Nissan parameter (d) indicates the presence of strong molecular interactions due to appreciable dipole-dipole and dipole-induced dipole interactions¹³ while the negative values of d may be attributed to dominance of dispersion type of forces¹² between the like molecules. The last conclusion is in excellent agreement with the values of d (shown in Table 2) obtained from the experiment in our investigation.

Experimental

Tetrahydrofuran (THF, Merck) was kept for several days over KOH, refluxed for 24 h and distilled over LiAlH_4 as described earlier¹⁵. Normal pentane, hexane and heptane were purified according to the standard procedures^{16,17}. The purities were checked by density determination dilatometrically¹⁸ at (288.15, 293.15 and 298.15 K) ± 0.1 K which almost agreed within the accuracy of $\pm 1 \times 10^{-4}$ g cm^{-3} with the available literature^{19,20} values. All the mixtures were prepared volumetrically²¹ in stoppered bottles.

The densities (ρ) were measured with an Ostwald-Sprengel type pycnometer having a bulb volume of 25 cm^3 and an internal diameter of the capillary of about 0.1 cm. The pycnometer was calibrated at (288.15, 293.5 and 298.15) K with doubly distilled water and benzene. The pycnometer with the test solution was equilibrated in a water bath maintained at ± 0.01 K of the desired temperature by means of a mercury in glass thermoregulator, and the tem-

perature was determined with a calibrated thermometer and a Muller bridge. The pycnometer was then removed from the thermostatic bath, properly dried, and weighed. The evaporation losses remained insignificant during the time of actual measurements. Averages of triplicate measurements were taken into account. The density values were reproducible to $\pm 3 \times 10^{-5}$ g cm^{-3} . Details have been described earlier²².

The viscosities were measured by means of suspended-level Ubbelohde²⁴ viscometer at the desired temperature (accuracy ± 0.01 K). The precision of the viscosity measurements was 0.05%. Details have been described earlier²⁴.

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Choudhury *et al.* : Excess molar volume, excess energy and viscosity deviation of binary mixtures *etc.*

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